

Lesson Plan: Week 2 Jan 10-12

Learning outcomes / objectives:

1. Students will be able to demonstrate how patterns and repetition can create expectations in music.
2. Students will be able to identify imagined expectations for specific pieces of music based on pre-existing contexts.
3. Students will be able to demonstrate how to successfully fulfill or thwart expectations for musical effect.
4. Students will construct their own experiments for creating, fulfilling and subverting expectations within the context of a single piece of music.
5. Students will engage with the method of clarifying questions to define intention in a new piece of music and use that defined intention to guide the organization of sounds.

Materials

Students will receive a handout “Questions for Composing” and will need their primary instruments/an instrument for Wednesday's class.

Procedures / Methods

Mon Jan 10

1. Students will participate in a presentation and discussion on ‘building, meeting, and subverting musical expectations.’ They will have a clearly expressed understanding of what expectations can be, what it means to fulfill expectations, and what it means to subvert them. In a follow up activity, students will be presented with several musical examples and asked to describe how the music interacts with audience expectations.
2. Students will be assigned an experiment due by the start of the next class in which they write a 30 second musical example where they create musical expectations, and then in turn subvert, and fulfill them. Video and audio file with accompanying written instruction will be submitted virtually for a completion grade as part of the students participation assessment.

Wed Jan 12

1. Some students will volunteer to share their experiments with the class. Class will then discuss how their peers interpreted the experiment. Discussion will end with the teacher presenting an experiment that demonstrates several different methods of fulfilling the experiment qualifications.

2. Students will participate in a presentation and guided discussion on the writing process: “facing the blank page”. Students will receive the “questions for composing” handout and are guided through the process of answering clarifying questions to determine intention in writing a specific piece of music. Students then verbally demonstrate an understanding of how a well defined intention can determine how sound is organized by following the question process for an imaginary piece as a class.

Suggested Timeline

Mon Jan 10

1-2 Minutes - Introduction and announcements

15 Minutes - presentation on expectations ‘building, meeting, and subverting musical expectations.’

10 Minutes - Discussion on expectations in music.

10 Minutes - follow up activity where students identify expectations at play in several musical examples.

10 Minutes - overview of experiment 1.

1-2 Minutes - Recap of key takeaways and parting questions.

Wed Jan 12

20 Minutes - students share their experiments with the class for peer discussion.

5 Minutes - teacher experiment shared and explained with class.

10 Minutes - guided explanation of the “questions for composing” handout.

10 Minutes - class walk through an imagined piece through the “questions for composing” handout. Students will apply this process to their own piece and submit the answers online.

5 Minutes - Recap of key takeaways and parting questions.